

Electron Hole Liquid Formation in the Formamidinium Lead Bromide Perovskite

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We observe radiative recombination from an electron-hole liquid (EHL) in a thin film of FAPbBr₃, a metal halide perovskite used in transparent photovoltaics and light emitters. Photoluminescence (PL) at low excitation intensity and low temperatures only shows the free-exciton (FE) signal. As the excitation intensity increases, two additional signals in PL emerge: the electron-hole plasma (EHP) and the EHL recombination bands. For both the FE-EHP and the EHP-EHL phase transitions a critical carrier density is established and a phase diagram is presented.

In semiconductors, optical excitation at low fluences usually generates an ensemble of electron-hole pairs which form a non-interacting gas of excitons, usually called free-excitons (FE). Upon increasing the intensity of the optical excitation, because of the increasing dielectric screening of the Coulomb potential, excitons will tend not to form in favor of a gas of free electrons and holes, usually called an electron-hole plasma (EHP). This paradigm is the essence of the Mott transition [1], which predicts the existence of an insulator-metal transition at the so-called Mott density. Experimental evidence for the exciton-plasma Mott transition was given for the first time in silicon by Shah et al. in 1977 [2]. Furthermore, the renormalization effect of the electronic eigenstate in the EHP results in the formation of an electron-hole liquid (EHL) state below some critical temperature [3,4]. In analogy to the real gas case, this physical picture predicts a phase separation between the EHL and the surrounding gas of both excitons and free carriers. In contrast to the EHP, the EHL shows incompressibility, surface tension, and short-range order similarly to a classical liquid. The EHL has been observed at high intensity optical excitations in materials having long carrier lifetimes such as silicon [2,5,6], germanium [7,8], diamond [9–11], and GaP [12], as well as in bidimensional metal dichalcogenides [13,14]. While a cryogenic temperature is required for 3D materials, the strong electron confinement existing in 2D materials allows the observation of EHL even at room temperature.

The physics of EHPs and EHLs are fascinating from a fundamental point of view but their study also helps understand the fundamental properties of the materials in which they are observed, and have implications for their use in applications, in particular as light emitters. In this context, metal halide perovskites (MHPs), which are extensively used in photovoltaic applications [15] in part thanks to the long lifetime of photoexcited carriers can be a novel class of materials where the observation of electron-hole condensation could be expected. For our study we have chosen a material that finds applications in transparent photovoltaics [16,17] and light emitters [18,19], namely formamidinium lead bromide (FAPbBr₃). This material possesses a free exciton with a binding energy of

approximately 25 meV [20] and a carrier lifetime of tens to hundreds of nanoseconds [18,21] (see Figure S1 in the Supplemental Material for our estimation). In this paper, we present photoluminescence (PL) measurements on thin films of pure FAPbBr₃ as a function of temperature and excitation intensity and provide evidence for the formation of an EHL up to temperatures of about 100 K. A tentative phase diagram that includes the exciton-plasma Mott transition and the formation of the EHL is also reported. We underline that the EHL has been so far investigated in semiconductors with highly crystalline structure, since defects reduce the lifetime of the carriers thus hampering the formation of the EHL. Herein we report the formation of the EHL phase for a material where defects are not negligible. This important feature confirms the defect tolerance of metal halide perovskites [22–24]. Our study provides a fundamental insight into the optical properties of FAPbBr₃ and contributes to the understanding of the behavior of excitons and free carriers in this important compound that belongs to the MHP family, a class of materials that is driving an important progress in photovoltaics and optoelectronics.

The sample has been prepared as follows. 1.3M FABr (Dyesol) and 1.3M PbBr₂ (TCI) were weighted in a vial and dissolved in DMSO. The FAPbBr₃ solution was left to stir for 8 hours. 2.5 x 2.5 cm shaped glasses (1 mm thick) were first washed with a soap: water solution (5:100 in vv) and then rinsed with distilled water and isopropanol through ultrasonic baths of 10 minutes to remove organic impurities and dust from the substrates. Cleaned substrates undergo a UV light soaking treatment for 30 minutes to improve wettability for reaching a uniform layer deposition. FAPbBr₃ has been deposited under a N₂ atmosphere. Before perovskite deposition, the substrates were heated to 60 °C and 80 µl of the solution was dropped and spun at 4000 rpm on the hot sample for 20 seconds. Ten seconds after the beginning of the spin, 200 µl of ethyl acetate was added to help the perovskite crystallization. The samples were then annealed at 80°C for 10 minutes.

PL has been measured using the output at 500 nm (≈ 2.5 eV) of an optical parametric amplifier (OPA, Opera Solo-Coherent) with a pulse width duration of about 40 fs. The OPA is pumped by a

Ti:sapphire regenerative amplifier (Legend Elite - Coherent) operating at a repetition rate of 1 kHz, 35 fs of pulse duration, and 4 W power centered at 800 nm. The exciting beam was focused on the sample with a spot of about 100 μm diameter. A long-pass filter with the cut-off edge at 520 nm has been used to selectively eliminate the 500 nm light scattered by the sample. The PL signal was detected with a Peltier-cooled charge-coupled device (CCD) camera after having been dispersed in a 30 cm long monochromator with a 1200 grooves/mm grating. PL spectra were recorded at selected temperatures in the 12–100 K range by cooling down the sample with a closed-loop He cryostat. The photoexcited carrier density n_0 has been estimated using the following formula [25]

$$n_0 = \frac{F}{\hbar\omega} \cdot \frac{A}{d}$$

where $\hbar\omega$ is the laser photon energy, A is the absorptance approximated to 0.5 (see the details in Figure S2 of Supplemental Material), d is the sample thickness (200 nm). The measurements were performed for different incident laser fluences (F) ranging from 13 to 1020 $\mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$, which give rise to carrier densities ranging from of 8.0×10^{17} to $6.4 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The carrier density obtained in this way overestimates the true value because a homogeneous light intensity is considered over the whole sample thickness and laser spot diameter.

We have noticed the dramatic increase of defect-related luminescence after a temperature cycle. Therefore, all measurements were started at low T (12 K) after having checked the sample quality using the defect-related emission and then the temperature was raised. The main reason why we have used several samples is the thermal fragility of the samples, that should be considered when research on MHPs is carried out at low temperatures.

For the aforementioned reasons, in this work we changed the samples after we cooled down it at 12 K and heat it back at room temperature.

Figure 1 shows the PL spectra obtained at T=20 K (**Figure 1a**), 40 K (**Figure 1b**) and 100 K (**Figure 1c**) at carrier densities of 8.0×10^{17} , 4.0×10^{18} , and $3.2 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. At low carrier density ($8.0 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and T=20 K we observe the typical low temperature PL spectrum of the FAPbBr₃, with a peak centered at 2.18 eV that is attributed to the FE recombination and a shoulder (SP) at low energy that we attribute to recombination at defects [26], as this band is only visible at low temperatures and low fluences. Increasing the carrier density to intermediate values ($4.0 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), we see that a second broad feature appears, approximately centered at 2.20 eV, which we assign to the recombination of electron-hole pairs in an EHP. At the highest carrier density ($3.2 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) a third broad PL peak appears around 2.15 eV that we assign to electron-hole recombination in an EHL. The spectral line shape of EHP and EHL strongly depend on the temperature, with a clear broadening as the temperature decreases.

Figure 1: Photoluminescence spectra obtained at the carrier density respectively of 8.0×10^{17} , 4.0×10^{18} , and $3.2 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and at the temperatures of (a) 20 K, (b) 40 K, and (c) 100 K.

Since the line shapes of FE and EHL are independent of the carrier density, Shah and coworkers [2] suggest to identify the transition between FE to EHP (EHP to EHL) as the carrier density where the linewidth of the PL band manifests the change in its dependence on the fluence (i.e., of the carrier

density) at selected temperatures. As Shah, Combescot and Dayem write [2], the choice of the half maximum as a reference point is arbitrary, a different choice of the low energy point only shifts the numerical value of that energy. In our case the EHP and EHL bands are difficult to distinguish in their entirety, and therefore we have taken our reference point to be the energy difference between the FE position and that of one fifth of the maximum PL intensity on the low energy side of the PL spectrum band (hereafter LEFM), where, at the highest excitation densities, the EHP contribution can be neglected and the signal can be safely attributed only to the EHL recombination. As can be seen in **Figure 1**, the energy position of the FE is not exactly the same in all cases. This is due to the use of several distinct samples for this work that present some fluctuations of the FE energy due to small fluctuations of the FAPbBr₃ stoichiometry, as seen in other perovskites [27] (for further details see the section “Photoluminescence” in Experimental Methods). Following the suggestion given by Shah and coworkers, we report the energy difference between the FE energy and the LEFM energy of the PL band at the temperatures of 20, 40 and 100 K in **Figure 2**. Following the description of **Figure 1** for increasing fluence, the FE first dissociates to form an EHP and then, at higher densities an EHL forms. The first transition, the Mott transition, is indicated by a blue-grey arrow in **Figure 2** that represents the carrier density at which the PL spectrum starts to broaden and the FE-LEFM energy difference increases. This is due to the increase of the band-gap renormalization as the carrier density in the plasma increases [28]. Since the line shapes become constant at carrier densities higher than a critical value (e.g., $1.6 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ at 20 K), we define that carrier density as the critical density for EHL condensation (violet arrow). The critical value depends on the temperature and this aspect will lead to a phase diagram that is reported in **Figure 3**, as discussed below.

Figure 2: Plots of the energy differences between the position of the free exciton (FE) and the low-energy full-height-fifth-maximum (LEFM) as a function of the photogenerated carrier density at different temperatures. The experimental points obtained at the temperatures of 20, 40 and 100 K are represented by blue, orange, and green points, respectively, while the dashed lines are a guide to the eye. Blue-grey arrows indicate the EHP transition while purple arrows indicate the EHL transition.

Based on our findings, we construct a phase diagram for the e-h population in FAPbBr₃. **Figure 3** shows that the phase diagram reveals the stability regions of the different phases and their relative coexistence region, shedding light on the intricate carrier phase transition of the material. The plasma side of the coexistence curve (i.e., Mott transition, grey scattered points) is determined by taking the experimental carrier density, at which we observe an increase of the PL linewidth characteristic for the EHP (blue arrows in **Figure 2**), while the EHP-EHL transition (red scattered points) is determined to be the carrier densities, at which the linewidth stops increasing (purple arrows in **Figure 2**). The experimental EHP transition lies within the range of 10^{18} - 10^{19} cm⁻³ in the temperature range of 20 to 100 K. To have a direct comparison between the experimental data and theoretical evaluations, here we discuss two approaches to estimate the Mott density. The most common approach is based on the qualitative criterion for the existence of bound states. In the simplest approach, the Mott density

occurs when the mean exciton distance is approximately equal to the exciton Bohr radius (a_x) [29], the so called Mott criterion, leading to

$$n_M \approx \frac{1}{a_x^3} = \left(\frac{\mu/m_e}{a_B \epsilon_{eff}} \right)^3 = 1.6 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3} \quad (1)$$

where $a_x = 3.9 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}$, a_B is the Bohr radius, $\epsilon_{eff}=8.42$ is the effective dielectric screening, and $\mu/m_e=0.115$ is the excitonic reduced mass [20]. This model is very simple and temperature-independent, and usually overestimates the carrier density: as can be seen in **Figure 3** where the model prediction (grey line) is compared to the experimental data it only grasps the order of magnitude. A more complex approach that allows for a better estimation of the Mott density defines a screening length in the Debye-Hückel approximation. The energy distributions of the carriers follow a Boltzmann distribution and we point out that it is a delicate assumption in conditions of a degenerate carrier distribution (i.e. very low temperature regimes) [29,30].

It follows:

$$n_M^{DH} = 0.708 \frac{kT}{a_x^3 R y^*} \approx 4.2 \cdot 10^{16} \frac{\text{cm}^{-3}}{\text{K}} \cdot T(\text{K}) \quad (2)$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant, $R y^*$ is the exciton binding energy, and T is the temperature.

The blue line in **Figure 3** shows that the theoretical result is in good agreement with the experimental data. A more sophisticated description of the Mott density could be in principle calculated ab-initio involving the so-called random-phase approximation (RPA) [31]; however, this approach is beyond the scope of this article, which is intended to provide an experimental demonstration of EHL formation in MHPs.

The large linewidth of the PL bands of MHPs makes a quantitative analysis of results that critically depend on the linewidth analysis difficult, and this is the source of the quantitative uncertainties found in our analysis. Nevertheless, the FE-EHP and EHP-EHL phase transitions have been clearly observed in our experiments and a fair agreement with the Mott model based on the Debye-Hückel

approximation has been found. It will be intriguing to study in the future other MHPs with different halide composition, and dimensionality to form a large set of data that will allow a better and reliable picture of the electron-hole pair physics in this important class of materials.

Figure 3: Electron-hole phase diagram of FAPbBr₃ where the black squares and the red dots are our experimental data relative to the EHP and EHL formation as described in **Figure 2**. The grey area indicates the coexistence area of EHP and EHL. The grey vertical line indicates the Mott density estimated with the Mott criterion, while the blue line is the theoretical curve after the equation 2. The grey-red line is a guide to the eye for the EHP and EHL transition.

In conclusion, temperature-dependent and fluence-dependent PL measurements on formamidinium lead bromide have shed light on the Mott transition and on the formation of the EHL in MHPs. Our experimental results have allowed us to sketch a first phase diagram of the electron-hole pair system on perovskites, in which the critical carrier densities and temperature for the FE-EHP and EHP-EHL transitions have been determined.

Our study opens a new field of research in MHPs that, with the investigation of different halide composition and dimensionality, will give a clearer insight into the properties of photoexcited carriers in this technologically relevant class of materials.

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